

RESEARCH ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 11-11-2023

Accepted: 02-12-2023

Published: 05-01-2024

Citation: Tiwari S, Dewangan LK (2024) Fixed Point and Common Fixed Point Theorems for Single Valued and Multivalued Mappings in Partial b -Metric Spaces. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 17(1): 59-64. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i1.2853>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Fixed Point and Common Fixed Point Theorems for Single Valued and Multivalued Mappings in Partial b -Metric Spaces

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Abstract

Objectives: To prove some fixed point theorems and common fixed point theorems by using partial b -metric spaces. **Methods:** Ciric type contraction for single-valued mapping is also used to prove fixed point theorem and Nadler's type Banach contraction is used to produce fixed point and common fixed point theorems. **Findings:** We have to find fixed point and common fixed point theorems for single valued mapping and a fixed point theorem for multivalued mapping. **Novelty :** We have to use a new type of space called partial b -metric space to prove all the theorems in this paper. No one has proven these theorems before in this space.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification : 47H10, 54H25.**Keywords:** Partial b -metric space; Single valued; Multi valued; Common fixed point; Fixed point

1 Introduction

An essential part of functional and nonlinear analysis is fixed point theory. Banach⁽¹⁾ presented an important finding regarding contraction maps. Since then, other writers have contributed numerous papers that deal with fixed point results (see, for example,⁽²⁻⁴⁾).

More recently, Shukla⁽⁵⁾ expanded upon the notions of b -metric spaces and partial metric spaces, introducing the concept of partial b -metric spaces. In this context, Shukla not only formulated the Banach contraction principle but also established a Kannan-type fixed point theorem within partial b -metric spaces.

The aforementioned spaces have seen a great deal of development. The aforementioned spaces have recently been the focus of investigation into fixed point and common fixed point results for single-valued as well as multi-valued mappings; for examples, see Ali et al.⁽⁶⁾, Khan et al.⁽⁷⁾, Kanwel et al.⁽⁸⁻¹⁰⁾, Tassaddiq et al.⁽¹¹⁾, Karapinar et al.^(12,13), Qawaqneh et al.⁽¹⁴⁾, Shoaib et al.⁽¹⁵⁾, and the references within it.

This work is dedicated to the formulation and proof of contractive mappings fixed point theorems in partial b -metric spaces. The application of contraction of the Ciric⁽¹⁶⁾ type is used in Theorem 3.1 to determine a fixed point of a single-valued map and provide an extension in partial b -metric space. Theorem 3.2 uses Banach⁽¹⁾ type

contraction in the setting of complete partial b-metric spaces to expand Nadler’s fixed point theorem⁽¹⁷⁾. A fixed point theorem for multi-valued mapping in partial b-metric spaces was demonstrated by Theorem 3.3.

2 Preliminaries

Firstly, we recall some basic definitions,

Definition 2.1⁽⁵⁾ Let X be a non-empty set and the self mapping $d : X \times X \rightarrow R^+$ (R^+ stands for non-negative reals) satisfies:

(Pb1) $x = y$ if and only if $d(x, x) = d(x, y) = d(y, y)$;

(Pb2) $d(x, x) \leq d(x, y)$;

(Pb3) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$;

(Pb4) there exist a real number $s \geq 1$ such that $d(x, y) \leq s[d(x, z) + d(z, y)] - d(z, z)$.

Then d is called a partial b -metric on X and (X, d) is called a partial b -metric space with coefficient s .

Definition 2.2 Let $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in a partial b -metric space (X, d) . Then:

(1) The sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to be a convergent in (X, d) , if there exists $x^* \in X$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x^*) = 0$.

(2) The sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to be a Cauchy sequence in (X, d) , if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a positive $n_0 \in N$ such that $d(x_n, x_m) < \varepsilon$ for all $n, m > n_0$ (or, equivalently, $\lim_{n, m \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x_m) = 0$).

(3) (X, d) is called a complete partial b -metric space if every Cauchy sequence is convergent in X .

Definition 2.3 Let X be a non-empty set. Then a self-mapping $T : X \rightarrow X$ is said to be a fixed point if for all $x \in X$ such that $T(x) = x$.

Example 2.4 The mapping $T : R \rightarrow R$ defined by $T(x) = \sin x$ has 0 as a fixed point.

Definition 2.5 A pair of self-mappings have a common fixed point $S, T : X \rightarrow X$ is a point $a \in X$ for which

$$S(a) = T(a) = a.$$

Definition 2.6 Consider a metric space (X, d) . Let $CB(X)$ denote the family of all non-empty bounded and closed subsets of X . Suppose that a map $H : CB(X) \times CB(X) \rightarrow R$ for $U, V \in CB(X)$, define

$$H(U, V) = \max\{ \sup_{u \in U} \inf_{v \in V} d(u, v), \sup_{v \in V} \inf_{u \in U} d(u, v) \}$$

where $d(u, V) = \inf\{d(u, v) : v \in V\}$ is the distance of a point u to the set V . This H is a metric on $CB(X)$, called Housdorff metric induced by the metric d .

Definition 2.7⁽¹⁸⁾ Let a multi-valued mapping $T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ on a non-empty set X , $CB(X)$ be the family of all non-empty closed and bounded subsets of X . A point $y \in X$ is called fixed point of T if $y \in Ty$.

Lemma 2.8⁽¹⁸⁾ Let partial b -metric space (X, d) and let $CB(X)$ is the family of all non-empty closed and bounded subsets of X . Then, for $U, V \in CB(X)$,

(1) $d(a, U) \leq H(U, V), a \in U$;

(2) For $\varepsilon > 0$ and $a \in U, \exists b \in V$ such that

$$d(a, b) \leq H(U, V) + \varepsilon$$

3 Result and Discussion

In this paper, we begin with the proof of the following result in partial b -metric space with the help of single valued mapping:

Theorem 3.1 Let a (X, d, s) be a complete partial b -metric space with $s \geq 1$ and $T : X \rightarrow X$ is a single valued mapping, such that

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \alpha_1 d(x, y) + \alpha_2 d(x, Tx) + \alpha_3 d(y, Ty) + \alpha_4 [d(y, Tx) + d(x, Ty)],$$

where $\alpha_1 + (1 + s)\alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + (1 + s)\alpha_4 < 1, \forall x, y \in X$. Then, $\exists x^* \in X$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x^*$ and x^* is the unique fixed point.

Proof. Let $x_0 \in X$ and $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in X define as

$$x_n = Tx_n = T^n x_0, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &= d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \\ &\leq \alpha_1 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \alpha_2 d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) + \alpha_3 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + \alpha_4 [d(x_n, x_n) + d(x_{n-1}, x_{n+1})] \\ &\leq \alpha_1 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \alpha_2 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \alpha_3 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \alpha_4 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + s\alpha_4 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + s\alpha_4 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) - \alpha_4 d(x_n, x_n) \\ &\leq \alpha_1 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \alpha_2 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + \alpha_3 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \alpha_4 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ &\quad + s\alpha_4 d(x_{n-1}, x_n) + s\alpha_4 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \\ (1 - \alpha_3 - \alpha_4 - s\alpha_4)d(x_n, x_{n+1}) &\leq (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + s\alpha_4)d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \end{aligned}$$

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \left(\frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + s\alpha_4}{1 - \alpha_3 - \alpha_4 - s\alpha_4} \right) d(x_{n-1}, x_n),$$

where $k = \frac{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + s\alpha_4}{1 - \alpha_3 - \alpha_4 - s\alpha_4}$.

Therefore,

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq kd(x_{n-1}, x_n) \leq k^2 d(x_{n-2}, x_{n-1}).$$

Continuing this process, we get

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq k^n d(x_0, x_1).$$

Consider $m, n \in N$ with $m > n$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_n, x_m) &\leq s[d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, x_m)] - d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+1}) \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + sd(x_{n+1}, x_m) \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s\{s[d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + d(x_{n+2}, x_m)] - d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+2})\} \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s^2 d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + s^2 d(x_{n+2}, x_m) \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s^2 d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + s^3 d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}) + \dots + s^m d(x_{n+m-1}, x_{n+m}) \\ &\leq sk^n d(x_0, x_1) + s^2 k^{n+1} d(x_0, x_1) + s^3 k^{n+2} d(x_0, x_1) + \dots + s^m k^{n+m-1} d(x_0, x_1) \\ &\leq sk^n d(x_0, x_1) [1 + sk + (sk)^2 + \dots + (sk)^{m-1}] \\ &\leq sk^n d(x_0, x_1) \left[\frac{1 - (sk)^m}{1 - sk} \right], \end{aligned}$$

when $m, n \rightarrow \infty$, $d(x_n, x_m) \rightarrow 0$. Hence, $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Since X is complete, $\{x_n\}$ converges to an element of X , say $x^* \in X$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} d(x^*, Tx^*) &\leq s[d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, Tx^*)] - d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+1}) \\ &\leq sd(x^*, x_{n+1}) + sd(Tx_n, Tx^*) \\ &\leq sd(x^*, x_{n+1}) + s\alpha_1 d(x_n, x^*) + s\alpha_2 d(x_n, Tx_n) + s\alpha_3 d(x^*, Tx^*) \\ &\quad + s\alpha_4 d(x^*, Tx_n) + s\alpha_4 d(x_n, Tx^*) \\ &\leq sd(x^*, x_{n+1}) + s\alpha_1 d(x_n, x^*) + s\alpha_2 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s\alpha_3 d(x^*, Tx^*) \\ &\quad + s\alpha_4 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + s\alpha_4 \{s[d(x_n, x^*) + d(x^*, Tx^*)] - d(x^*, x^*)\} \\ &\leq sd(x^*, x_{n+1}) + s\alpha_1 d(x_n, x^*) + s\alpha_2 d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s\alpha_3 d(x^*, Tx^*) \\ &\quad + s\alpha_4 d(x^*, x_{n+1}) + s^2 \alpha_4 d(x_n, x^*) + s^2 \alpha_4 d(x^*, Tx^*) \\ d(x^*, Tx^*) &\leq \frac{(s + s\alpha_4)}{(1 - s\alpha_3 - s^2 \alpha_4)} d(x^*, a_{n+1}) + \frac{(s\alpha_1 + s^2 \alpha_4)}{(1 - s\alpha_3 - s^2 \alpha_4)} d(a_n, x^*) + \frac{s\alpha_2}{(1 - s\alpha_3 - s^2 \alpha_4)} d(a_n, a_{n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

taking $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$d(x^*, Tx^*) \leq \frac{(s + s\alpha_4)}{(1 - s\alpha_3 - s^2 \alpha_4)} d(x^*, x^*) + \frac{(s\alpha_1 + s^2 \alpha_4)}{(1 - s\alpha_3 - s^2 \alpha_4)} d(x^*, x^*) + \frac{s\alpha_2}{(1 - s\alpha_3 - s^2 \alpha_4)} d(x^*, x^*),$$

implies that $x^* = Tx^*$. Hence, x^* is a fixed point of T .

For uniqueness, assume that y^* is another fixed point of T . Then, we have $Ty^* = y^*$.

Consider,

$$\begin{aligned} d(x^*, y^*) &= d(Tx^*, Ty^*) \\ &\leq \alpha_1 d(x^*, y^*) + \alpha_2 d(x^*, Tx^*) + \alpha_3 d(y^*, Ty^*) + \alpha_4 [d(y^*, Tx^*) + d(x^*, Ty^*)] \\ &\leq \alpha_1 d(x^*, y^*) + \alpha_2 d(x^*, x^*) + \alpha_3 d(y^*, y^*) + \alpha_4 [d(y^*, x^*) + d(x^*, y^*)] \\ &\leq \alpha_1 d(x^*, y^*) + \alpha_2 d(x^*, y^*) + \alpha_3 d(y^*, x^*) + \alpha_4 [d(y^*, x^*) + d(x^*, y^*)] \\ &\leq (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + 2\alpha_4) d(x^*, y^*), \end{aligned}$$

this implies that $x^* = y^*$.

Theorem 3.2 Consider a complete partial b metric space (X, d, s) with constant $s \geq 1$ and suppose that $F, G : X \rightarrow X$ be two maps, for which $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in [0, \frac{1}{3})$ such that

$$d(Fa, Gb) \leq \eta_1 d(a, b) + \eta_2 [d(a, Fb) + d(a, Gb)].$$

Then there exists a common fixed point of F and G .

Proof. Let $x_0 \in X$. Consider the sequence $\{x_n\}$ so that $x_{2n+2} = Gx_{2n+1}, x_{2n+1} = Fx_{2n}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) &= d(Fx_{2n}, Gx_{2n+1}) \\ &\leq \eta_1 d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}) + \eta_2 [d(x_{2n}, Fx_{2n}) + d(x_{2n+1}, Gx_{2n+1})] \\ &\leq \eta_1 d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}) + \eta_2 d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) + \eta_2 d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}), \\ (1 - \eta_2) d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) &\leq (\eta_1 + \eta_2) d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}), \\ d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) &\leq \left[\frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2}{(1 - \eta_2)} \right] d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}) \leq kd(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}), \end{aligned}$$

where $k = \left[\frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2}{(1 - \eta_2)} \right]$. As $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in [0, \frac{1}{3})$. So $\eta_1 + 2\eta_2 < 1 \Rightarrow \eta_1 + \eta_2 < 1 - \eta_2$.

This implies that $\frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2}{(1 - \eta_2)} < 1$, i.e. $k < 1$. So,

$$d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) \leq kd(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}) \leq k^2d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2n}).$$

Continuing this process, we obtain

$$d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) \leq k^n d(x_0, x_1).$$

In general,

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq k^n d(x_0, x_1).$$

Now, let $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m > n$

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_n, x_m) &\leq s[d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, x_m)] - d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+1}) \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + sd(x_{n+1}, x_m) \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s\{s[d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + d(x_{n+2}, x_m)] - d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+2})\} \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s^2d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + s^2d(x_{n+2}, x_m) \\ &\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s^2d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + s^3d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}) + \dots + s^{m-n}d(x_{m-1}, x_m) \\ &\leq sk^n d(x_0, x_1) + s^2k^{n+1}d(x_0, x_1) + s^3k^{n+2}d(x_0, x_1) + \dots + s^{m-n}k^{m-1}d(x_0, x_1) \\ d(x_n, x_m) &\leq sk^n d(x_0, x_1) \frac{1-(sk)^m}{1-sk}. \end{aligned}$$

When $m, n \rightarrow \infty, \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x_m) = 0$.

Hence, $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Since X is complete, $\{x_n\}$ converges to $y \in X$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} d(y, Gy) &\leq s[d(y, Fx_{2n}) + d(Fx_{2n}, Gy)] - d(Fx_{2n}, Fx_{2n}) \\ &\leq sd(y, Fx_{2n}) + sd(Fx_{2n}, Gy) \\ &\leq sd(y, x_{2n+1}) + s[\eta_1 d(x_{2n}, y) + \eta_2 d(y, Gy) + \eta_2 d(x_{2n}, Fx_{2n})] \\ &\leq sd(y, x_{2n+1}) + s\eta_1 d(x_{2n}, y) + s\eta_2 d(y, Gy) + s\eta_2 d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}) \\ (1 - s\eta_2)d(y, Gy) &\leq sd(y, x_{2n+1}) + s\eta_1 d(x_{2n}, y) + s\eta_2 d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}) \\ d(y, Gy) &\leq \frac{s}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, x_{2n+1}) + \frac{s\eta_1}{1-s\eta_2} d(x_{2n}, y) + \frac{s\eta_2}{1-s\eta_2} d(x_{2n}, x_{2n+1}). \end{aligned}$$

When $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\begin{aligned} d(y, Gy) &\leq \frac{s}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, y) + \frac{s\eta_1}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, y) + \frac{s\eta_2}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, y) \\ d(y, Gy) &\leq \frac{s}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, Gy) + \frac{s\eta_1}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, Gy) + \frac{s\eta_2}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, Gy) \\ d(y, Gy) &\leq 0, \end{aligned}$$

this implies that $y = Gy$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} d(y, Fy) &\leq s[d(y, Gx_{2n+1}) + d(Gx_{2n+1}, Fy)] - d(Gx_{2n+1}, Gx_{2n+1}) \\ d(y, Fy) &\leq sd(y, Gx_{2n+1}) + sd(Gx_{2n+1}, Fy) \\ d(y, Fy) &\leq sd(y, x_{2n+2}) + s\eta_1 d(x_{2n+1}, y) + s\eta_2 d(x_{2n+1}, Gx_{2n+1}) + s\eta_2 d(y, Fy) \\ (1 - s\eta_2)d(y, Fy) &\leq sd(y, x_{2n+2}) + s\eta_1 d(x_{2n+1}, y) + s\eta_2 d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}) \\ d(y, Fy) &\leq \frac{s}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, x_{2n+2}) + \frac{s\eta_1}{1-s\eta_2} d(x_{2n+1}, y) + \frac{s\eta_2}{1-s\eta_2} d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n+2}), \end{aligned}$$

when $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\begin{aligned} d(y, Fy) &\leq \frac{s}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, y) + \frac{s\eta_1}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, y) + \frac{s\eta_2}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, y) \\ d(y, Fy) &\leq \frac{s}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, Fy) + \frac{s\eta_1}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, Fy) + \frac{s\eta_2}{1-s\eta_2} d(y, Fy), \end{aligned}$$

this implies that $y = Fy$.

Thus, $Gy = Fy = y$. Hence, y is a common fixed point of G and F .

Now, we will prove a fixed point theorem for multi-valued mappings in partial b -metric space:

Theorem 3.3 Let (X, d) be a complete partial b -metric space with constant $s \geq 1$. Let $G : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ is a multivalued mapping defined as

$$H(Gx, Gy) \leq \alpha d(x, y), \forall x, y \in X \text{ and } \alpha \in [0, 1), s \geq 1.$$

Then, there exists $x \in X$ such that $y \in Gy$.

Proof. Suppose that $x_0 \in X, Gx_0 \neq \emptyset$ is closed and bounded subset of X . Also, let $x_1 \in Gx_0, Gx_1 \neq \emptyset$ be closed and bounded subset of X . By lemma 2.8, there exists $x_2 \in Gx_1$ such that

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq H(Gx_0, Gx_1) + \alpha.$$

Now, $Gx_2 \neq \emptyset$ closed and bounded subsets of X , there exists $x_3 \in Gx_2$ such that

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq H(Gx_1, Gx_2) + \alpha^2. \tag{3.3.1}$$

By using contraction condition,

$$d(x_2, x_3) \leq d(x_1, x_2) + \alpha^2,$$

$$d(x_3, x_4) \leq H(Gx_2, Gx_3) + \alpha^3$$

$$\leq \alpha d(x_2, x_3) + \alpha^3.$$

Using Equation (3.3.1), we have

$$d(x_3, x_4) \leq \alpha[d(x_1, x_2) + \alpha^2] + \alpha^3$$

$$\leq \alpha^2 d(x_1, x_2) + 2\alpha^3$$

$$\leq \alpha^2 [H(Gx_0, Gx_1) + \alpha] + 2\alpha^3$$

$$\leq \alpha^2 [\alpha d(x_0, x_1) + \alpha] + 2\alpha^3$$

$$\leq \alpha^3 d(x_0, x_1) + \alpha^3 + 2\alpha^3$$

$$\leq \alpha^3 d(x_0, x_1) + 3\alpha^3.$$

In general,

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \alpha^n d(x_0, x_1) + n\alpha^n.$$

For convenience, we set $d(x_n, x_{n+1}) = d_n$, so the above result can be written as

$$d_n \leq \alpha^n d_0 + n\alpha^n.$$

For $m, n \in N, m \geq n$, we have

$$d(x_n, x_m) \leq s[d(x_n, x_{n+1}) + d(x_{n+1}, x_m)] - d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+1})$$

$$\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + sd(x_{n+1}, x_m)$$

$$\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s\{s[d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + d(x_{n+2}, x_m)] - d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+2})\}$$

$$\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s^2 d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + s^2 d(x_{n+2}, x_m)$$

$$\leq sd(x_n, x_{n+1}) + s^2 d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + s^3 d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}) + \dots + s^{m-n} d(x_{m-1}, x_m)$$

$$\leq s\alpha^n d(x_0, x_1) + s^2 \alpha^{n+1} d(x_0, x_1) + s^3 \alpha^{n+2} d(x_0, x_1) + \dots + s^{m-n} \alpha^{m-1} d(x_0, x_1)$$

$$+ s n \alpha^n + s(n+1)\alpha^{n+1} + s^2(n+2)\alpha^{n+2} + \dots + s^{m-n}(m-1)\alpha^{m-1}$$

$$\leq s\alpha^n d(x_0, x_1) [1 + s\alpha + (s\alpha)^2 + \dots + s^{m-n-1} \alpha^{m-n-1}] + \sum_{i=n}^{m-1} i s^{i-n+1} \alpha^i$$

$$\leq s\alpha^n d(x_0, x_1) \left[\frac{1 - (s\alpha)^{m-n-1}}{1 - s\alpha} \right] + \sum_{i=n}^{m-1} i s^{i-n+1} \alpha^i.$$

In the limiting case when $m, n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$d(x_n, x_m) = 0,$$

this implies that $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X , the completeness of X implies that there exists $y \in X$ such that,

$$x_n \rightarrow y.$$

Now we will prove that y is a fixed point of G .

$$d(y, Gy) \leq s[d(y, x_n) + d(x_n, Gy)] - d(x_n, x_n) \leq sd(y, x_n) + sd(x_n, Gy).$$

By Lemma 2.8,

$$d(y, Gy) \leq d(y, x_n) + sH(Gx_{n-1}, Gy)$$

$$\leq sd(y, x_n) + s\alpha d(x_{n-1}, y).$$

In the limiting case when $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$d(y, Gy) \leq sd(y, y) + s\alpha d(y, y)$$

$$\leq sd(y, Gy) + s\alpha d(y, Gy)$$

$$(1 - s - s\alpha)d(y, Gy) \leq 0.$$

This implies that $y \in Gy$. Hence, y is a fixed point of G .

4 Conclusion

The use of fixed point techniques is both appealing and extremely helpful. This theory has potential applications to discrete dynamics for set-valued operators, functional inclusions, optimization theory, fractal graphics, and other nonlinear functional analysis domains. We have generalized and demonstrated fixed point and common fixed point theorems for single-valued mappings obeying Ciric type contractions in partial b -metric space. One fixed point theorem for multi-valued mappings with Nadler's type contractions has also been established in these spaces. Future studies could find these generalizations to be helpful.

5 Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the referees/Editors of Indian Journal of Science and Technology for all the useful comments and suggestions.

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